

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ag^+ Catalysed Oxidation of Dicarboxylic Acids by Peroxydisulphate Ion-Oxidation of Malonic, Succinic and Adipic Acids

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The kinetics of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of three typical dicarboxylic acids—succinic acid, adipic acid and malonic acid by peroxydisulphate ion in aqueous medium has been investigated. In all the three cases, the reaction is found to be first order in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and in the catalyst Ag^+ and zero order in substrate. However, the first order rate constant is found to be slightly dependent on the concentration of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ as well as on the concentration of substrate which may be ascribed to trace impurity. The reaction exhibits negative salt effect of the exponential type and also shows specific inhibitory effect. The energy parameters determined in each case show a close similarity. The reaction is inhibited by traces of allyl acetate. The products of oxidation identified in each case are: Succinic acid—tartaric acid and oxalacetic acid; Malonic acid—meso-oxalic acid, formaldehyde and CO_2 ; Adipic acid—monoketo adipic acid and levulinic acid. Considered with the above observations, a radical chain mechanism has been proposed and the corresponding rate expression derived.

PEROXYDISULPHATE ion has been used to oxidise a number of organic compounds and the kinetics of these reactions has been the subject of study of a large number of workers, as reviewed by House¹. However, a review of literature shows that, inspite of a large number of work, there is lack of general agreement on the mechanism of many of these reactions e.g., for the oxidation of the first dicarboxylic acid—oxalic acid. A survey of literature shows that little work appears to have been done on the kinetics of oxidation of higher dicarboxylic acids by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, the only study reported being the kinetic study of uncatalysed oxidation of malonic acid². Hence a detailed kinetic study of the Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of three dicarboxylic acids—malonic, succinic and adipic acids by peroxy-

disulphate ion has been carried out by us, the results of which are reported in this paper.

Experimental

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, AgNO_3 , substrates and other reagents used were either of E. Merck (G.R.) or B.D.H. (AnalaR) grade and $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ was used after recrystallization with double distilled water. The progress of reaction was followed by estimating unreacted peroxydisulphate, using iodometric method given by Szabo, Csanyi and Galiba³, as modified by Khulbe and Srivastava⁴.

Stoichiometry and product analysis

It is found that two moles of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ are consumed by one mole of the acid according to the stoichiometric equations:

Mono keto adipic acid undergoing decarboxylation to give levulinic acid (VI) accompanied by brisk evolution of CO₂.

Products I, IV, V and VI were identified by preparation of their respective 2, 4-dinitro phenyl hydrazones, while formaldehyde(II) was detected by conventional tests as well as by preparation of its hydrazone. The presence of oxal acetic acid (IV) was also confirmed by thin layer chromatography⁵ and two dimensional chromatography⁶. The formation of tartaric acid (III) was detected by paper chromatography and confirmed by ammonium vanadate and sodium nitroprusside tests.

Order of reaction

In each case, the reaction, for any kinetic run, is found to be first order in peroxydisulphate and zero order in organic acids, as evaluated by Vant Hoff differential method by employing initial rates determined by 'Plane mirror method'. The specific rate is found to be first order in Ag⁺ concentration in all the three cases. However, the first order rate constant is found to decrease slightly with increase in K₂S₂O₈ concentration at constant ionic strength and constant K⁺ concentration (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF K₂S₂O₈ AT CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH

[Substrate] = 0.01M; [AgNO₃] = 0.001M; Temp. = 35°

K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ (M)	K ₂ SO ₄ (M)	k' × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	Malonic acid k × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	Succinic acid k × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	Adipic acid k × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)
0.01	0.04	1.03	1.82	1.04	0.95
0.02	0.03	0.92	1.48	1.00	0.90
0.03	0.02	0.90	1.40	0.97	0.87
0.04	0.01	0.87	1.34	0.94	0.84
0.05	0.00	0.80	1.30	0.93	0.83

k' = specific rate for self decomposition.
k = net specific rate for oxidation of organic substrate.

Similarly, increase in concentration of the reductant slightly decreases the specific rate in all the three cases (Table 2).

Similar results have been observed by other workers also in the case of other substrates⁹⁻¹⁰. This slight decrease in specific rate with increase in substrate concentration may be due to an alternative equilibrium process H⁺ + S₂O₈²⁻ ⇌ HS₂O₈⁻ taking place preferentially at lower pH and thus affecting the equilibrium process with Ag⁺. Since this slight dependence of rate constant on the concentration of the oxidant as well as that of substrate has been observed at constant ionic strength and constant K⁺

concentration, the possible cause for it may also be traced to trace impurities present in the reactants¹¹. The dependence of the specific rate on the concentration of the oxidant as well as on the substrate

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION

[K₂S₂O₈] = 0.01M; [AgNO₃] = 0.001M; Temp. = 35°
k' = 1.54 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹.

Substrate (M)	Malonic acid k × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	Succinic acid k × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	Adipic acid k × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)
0.01	1.59	1.38	1.17
0.02	—	1.30	0.95
0.03	1.27	—	0.81
0.04	—	1.25	0.71
0.05	1.16	—	0.64
0.06	—	1.20	—
0.07	1.08	—	—
0.08	—	1.18	—
0.10	1.00	—	—

concentration suggests that the reaction follows a radical mechanism, which is supported by the fact that allyl acetate, a radical scavenger, inhibits the rate of reaction in all the three cases; the decrease in rate by the addition of 0.001M allyl acetate being nearly 10%, 13% and 20% for succinic acid, adipic acid and malonic acid oxidation respectively.

Salt effect

In all the cases, the salt effect (as determined by using K₂SO₄ as neutral salt) is negative and of primary exponential type suggesting that the rate determining process in all the three cases is between two oppositely charged ions.

The specific inhibitory effect of different cations followed a similar order in all the three reactions

Thermodynamic parameters

By a study of the three reactions at five different temperatures (30°-50°), the energy parameters were evaluated, as presented in Table 3.

A close similarity in the values of energy of activation, frequency factor, free energy of activation and entropy of activation in the three cases points to the fact that the three reactions follow a similar mechanism. A large negative value of entropy of activation has been earlier reported for Ag⁺ catalysed redox reactions of S₂O₈²⁻ with other substrates^{10,12-16} also. Further a large negative value of entropy of activation indicates that the formation of the activated complex involves a reaction either between two oppositely charged ions or between an ion and a neutral molecule.

Mechanism

In view of the above results and the formation of a complex between Ag⁺ and S₂O₈²⁻, as also proposed

by Bekier and Kijowski¹² and later on supported by Chaltykyan and Beileryan¹³ for other substrates,

Here it is seen that malic acid formed in stage 4 can react by two alternative paths and because of its immediate conversion into oxalacetic acid and tartaric acid, it is not detected in the reaction mixture by chromatographic analysis.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Temp. °A	$k \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)			
	Malonic acid	Succinic acid	Adipic acid	
303	—	1.06	—	
308	1.59	1.38	1.17	
313	2.16	1.81	1.40	
318	2.74	2.28	1.98	
323	3.56	3.08	2.48	
328	4.79	—	3.36	
Mean values	E (Kcal mole ⁻¹) $A \times 10^{-2}$ (sec ⁻¹) ΔG^\ddagger (Kcal mole ⁻¹) ΔS^\ddagger (E.U.)	10.7(±0.4) 7.15 25.0 -46.6	9.8(±0.5) 6.39 24.8 -47.8	10.9(±0.6) 10.90 25.2 -46.8

the following mechanism seems reasonable (taking succinic acid as an example) :

Applying the steady state treatment, the rate of disappearance of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, on the basis of above sequence of reactions, comes out to be

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1 K [\text{Ag}^+] [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] + k_4 [\text{R}] [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$$

and since,

$$k_1 K [\text{Ag}^+] [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] = k_4 [\text{R}] [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$$

hence,

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = 2k_1 K [\text{Ag}^+] [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$$

in conformity with the kinetic behaviour. However, in case of adipic acid, the monohydroxy adipic acid formed in stage 4 may only undergo stages 5 and 6 to yield mono-keto adipic acid (V), which decarboxylates to yield levulinic acid, as pointed out earlier.

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